

PILOT 11 GEVGELIJA-STRUMICA

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Main structure

1. Lessons learned
2. Main results achieved
3. Action Plan alignment and adoption
4. Pilot case study
5. Technical tools
6. Foresight tools (guides)

Pilot Leader: AgFutura

Pilot Partner: GGP

Lessons learned by working on foresight pilot

- Challenges
 - Poor data availability (regional and macro data) , technical capacity in key institutions, political instability (frequent changes of key policy decision makers), poor communication among institutions
- Changes in how region was viewed before and now
 - Changes in the perception of the region
 - Much better insights for the reasons of the current situation (needs of rural population not met, poor allocated budget and no consistency in policy)
- Recommendations to other regions facing similar challenges
 - Multistakeholder approach in policy creation (direct involvement of users)
 - Development and maintaining of technical capacity is highly important

Results

- Multi-stakeholder engagement
 - 38 members-14 female, surveys, meetings, discussion, events
- New insights and knowledge about the region
 - Solid **capacities** for attracting and maintaining population (available natural resources)
 - Poor **road infrastructure** and absence of other **infrastructural elements** supporting not only the rural economy but also the quality of life (eg. health care, daily care for kids, social care for elderly)
 - **Dynamic migration**, specifically of young population
- Tools as regional SDM
 - If relevant data available, very useful in future policy development, to draw conclusions for **designing policy options**
- Influence change in policies and/or attitudes
 - Significant **increase of awareness** among key stakeholders for the importance of using multistakeholder approach in policy development
 - **Higher understanding** of the negative effect of **poor involvement of marginalized interest groups** (young population, elderly people)

Action Plan

- Alignment with LTV4RA
 - Vision is based on **2 structural areas of interventions** (improving the capacity and the model of the rural extension; policy solutions dedicated to the young population in rural areas) that will have **multiplicative effect** in fostering rural attractiveness (stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous)
- Facilitating the AP adoption
 - **Organized event** (23.08.22) in the Ministry, RAP presented to Ministry and other stakeholders, adoption by relevant stakeholders, **positive response by the deputy Minister** to take over the process (new measures in programming, more funding)

Action Plan

No.	Actions	Funding/PO	Timeframe
1	Multi stakeholder workshop	AGFT/GGP	Done (23.08.2022)
2	Establishing a working group for structural reforms	MAFWE	September 2022- December 2022
3	Developing a specific Action plan	MAFWE	September 2022- December 2022
4	Plan for technical development	MAFWE, World Bank, EU funding, Development agencies funding (USAID, GIZ, SIPPO)	November 2022- March 2023
5	Developing a financial plan for support of measures for rural extension and young population	MAFWE, World Bank, EU funding, Development agencies funding (USAID, GIZ, SIPPO)	November 2022- March 2023
6	Working group transformed in a formal monitoring committee	MAFWE, World Bank, EU funding, Development agencies funding (USAID, GIZ, SIPPO)	April 2023 - 2030

Case study

- Intention to use pilot **case study from the compendium**
 - Parts of the compendium case study **regularly published and disseminated** via **web pages and social media accounts**
 - AP **presented and delivered** to the Ministry, will be disseminated via web pages and social media accounts
 - All materials will be disseminated in electronic version to regional stakeholders via **e-mail**
 - Specific **social media campaign** will be done for users to have information where all pilot results can be found (DiH, web pages)

Technical tools

- **Regional SDM:**
 - Agreed to be **presented upon requested** to the Ministry; Will be used in **consultancy** and other projects for policy creation
- **Semex:**
 - **Not applicable** in NMK due to language barrier
- **Rural Attractiveness Explorer:**
 - Will be continuously presented to **policy makers** as part of other projects with similar topics
- **Digital Innovation Hub:**
 - Specific **social media campaign**, or direct e-mails to policy developers (pilots page and all project results)
- **Atlas of Best Practices:**
 - Shared among **policy creators, consultants** as part of other projects with similar topics
 - Shared among **stakeholders and general public** in other national web portals to inspire and

Foresight tools (guides)

- Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)
 - Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)
 - Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)
 - The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change
 - D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology
- Will be used in **projects related to policy development, specific consultancy projects** with governmental institutions and regional government